

Disease intensity on flag leaves and panicles, unfilled grain percentage, and grain yield were measured. Flag leaf lesion counts and percentage of diseased grains/panicle were based on 50 randomly collected tillers/ plot.

Treatments differed significantly, but did not reduce flag leaf and grain infection much (see table). Grain infection was negatively correlated with percentage of unfilled grain ($r = -0.84^{**}$) and grain yield ($r = -0.84^{**}$),

but differences among the test fungicides were not significant. Blotter test determined that 75% of seeds collected from sprayed fields were associated with *H. oryzae*. That seed lot showed only 39% germination. □

Distribution and severity of rice seedling diseases in boro seedbeds in Bangladesh

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We surveyed rice seedbed diseases in some northwestern districts during the Nov-Mar boro season. Six diseases—bakanae (Bak), blast (Bl), brown spot (BS), damping-off (DO), root knot (RK), and seedling blight (Sb)—were found in 48 locations. Commonly grown rice were BR1, BR3, BR8, BR9, IR8, Pajam, Purbachi, and some local varieties.

DO was found everywhere, irrespective of variety (see table). RK was the second most common disease; it was not found in alkaline belts of Rajshahi district. Its intensity and severity were highest in sandy soil, especially near riverbanks, even in seedbeds with little standing water, irrespective of varieties sown.

BS was found in seedbeds that suffered from water stress. Bak affected seedlings of Purbachi, Khaily boro (local cultivar), and BR16. Bl was found mainly on Pajam and Iratom seedlings.

Distribution of seedling diseases as observed in boro seedbeds during January 1987 in northwestern districts of Bangladesh.

District	Disease frequency in survey area ^a						Total
	Bak	Bl	BS	DO	RK	Sb	
Bogra	6 (18.2)	0	6 (18.2)	12 (36.4)	9 (27.2)	0	33
Dinajpur	0	0	0	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	0	4
Gaibandha	2 (25.0)	0	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	0	8
Gazipur	0	2 (12.5)	1 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	2 (25.0)	1 (12.5)	8
Jalpur	1 (12.5)	0	1 (12.5)	3 (37.5)	3 (37.5)	0	8
Lalmonirhat	1 (33.3)	0	0	1 (33.3)	1 (33.3)	0	3
Mymensingh	2 (11.8)	3 (17.6)	3 (17.6)	6 (35.3)	3 (17.6)	0	17
Natore	1 (11.1)	0	3 (33.3)	3 (33.3)	2 (22.2)	0	9
Pabna	0	0	3 (37.5)	4 (50.0)	1 (12.5)	0	8
Rajshahi	0	0	2 (33.3)	2 (33.3)	1 (16.7)	1 (16.7)	6
Rangpur	2 (14.3)	1 (7.1)	1 (7.1)	5 (35.7)	5 (35.7)	0	14
Tangail	0	3 (16.7)	2 (11.1)	6 (33.3)	7 (38.9)	0	18
Total	15 (11.0)	9 (6.6)	24 (17.6)	48 (35.3)	38 (27.9)	2 (1.5)	136
DI	4 [3-5]	8 [7-9]	5 [3-7]	6 [3-9]	5 [3-7]	3 [1-5]	

^a Figures in parentheses show percentage of the disease in the district; those within brackets show disease index. DI 1 = lowest disease intensity, 9 = highest disease intensity.

Severity as high as disease index 8 was concentrated in Mymensingh, Tangail, Gazipur, and Rangpur districts. Sb was

found in only two locations. More than one disease was observed in the same seedbed in some locations. □

Managing rice sheath rot (ShR) disease in Kerala, India

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Field trials to evaluate crop nutrition schedules for managing rice ShR disease

have shown that sources of N and method of application can influence disease incidence and grain damage.

A field experiment during the first crop season (May-Sep 1985) at the Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana, used susceptible variety Jyothi to evaluate crop nutrition schedules for managing ShR.

The fertilizer level used was 70-35-52.5 kg NPK/ha, the recommended rate in disease endemic areas. Sources were

farmyard manure (FYM), urea, and ammonium sulfate for N; superphosphate for P; and muriate of potash for K. Except for FYM, all forms of N were applied in three splits, half as basal and half in two equal topdressings. K was applied in two equal splits, basal and as topdressing. All P was applied as basal.

Carboxin (0.1% spray), widely recommended for ShR control, was sprayed with two fertilizer treatments

Effect of fertilizer and organic manure on ShR intensity and rice grain yield. Kerala, India, 1985.

Treatment	Disease intensity ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Without fungicide (F ₀)	With fungicide (F ₁)	Without fungicide (F ₀)	With fungicide (F ₁)
Organic manure (OM) alone @ 5 t/ha in soil at planting	4.9	3.5	3.0	2.8
OM + N ₁ (urea) and K soil application	6.7	5.0	4.6	4.6
OM + N ₂ (ammonium sulfate) and K soil application	7.5	4.5	4.4	4.5
OM + N ₁ and K, last split of both N and K as foliar sprays	5.9	5.9	4.6	5.0
OM + N ₂ and K, last split of both N and K as foliar sprays	4.1	8.1	4.4	4.6
OM + N ₁ + K + Zn and Mn foliar sprays	8.2	6.1	4.6	4.7
OM + N ₂ + K + Zn and Mn foliar sprays	9.2	6.7	4.4	4.5
LSD for treatment (T)	2.1		197.1	
LSD for T × fungicide	3.0		—	

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice 1 to 9 scale.

45 and 60 d after transplanting.

Five random 1-m² samples were observed in each 24-m² plot. Each hill was scored on type and spread of lesions and on panicle damage. Average score for each plot was taken as disease intensity.

Urea was the best N source for yield; foliar application of N and K along with the fungicidal spray reduced panicle damage (see table).

We concluded that treatment improved the general health of the crop, especially in soils where the rate of absorption becomes poor with crop age. That, in turn, could reduce the rate of grain damage. □

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Greenhouse trials of seed dress method for controlling sheath blight (ShB)

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Rice grain-hull (1:4) culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn was incubated for 3-4 wk for use as inoculum. Baked soil was handmixed with the rice grain-hull culture at 3:2, then incubated for 1 wk. The mixture was transferred to plastic basins 18 cm in diameter.

Seed dressing used the slurry method of fungicidal application at 40 g/kg seeds, except 4 g PCNB/kg seeds with water added at 2-3% seed weight. Two days after transfer of incubated soil into the plastic basins, 100 treated seeds were planted. Percentages of germination and seedling infection were recorded 3 wk after planting. Controls were untreated seeds planted on uninfested soil and untreated seeds planted on infested soil. A completely randomized block design was used.

All fungicides tested were effective against *R. solani*, as shown by high

Germination, infection, and height and root length of UPLRi5 seedlings treated with fungicides, using the seed dress method, 21 d after sowing. UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (g/kg seeds)	Germination ^a (%)	Infection ^b (%)	Height ^c (cm)	Root length ^c (cm)
Benomyl	40	92.0 a	0.0 a	21.8	5.4
PCNB	4	95.6 a	0.0 a	22.4	6.2
Iprodione	40	91.3 a	0.0 a	20.6	6.7
EMDOC ^d	40	94.0 a	0.3 a	21.4	5.6
Benomyl-EMDOC	40-40	91.0 a	0.3 a	21.1	6.4
Benomyl-iprodione	40-40	90.3 a	0.0 a	20.9	7.7
EMDOC-iprodione	40-40	89.3 a	0.3 a	19.1	7.9
DHMu ^e - iprodione	40-40	81.6 b	0.4 a	22.5	7.4
Triphenyltin acetate-iprodione	40-40	92.0 a	0.3 a	19.6	4.8
Triphenyltin acetate-EMDOC	40-40	81.3 b	0.3 a	21.1	5.5
Triphenyltin acetate-triphenyltin hydroxide	40-40	81.6 b	1.2 a	18.3	2.9
Untreated seeds, inoculated soil	—	36.6 c	3.5 b	21.2	2.6
Untreated seeds, uninoculated soil	—	87.3 a	0.0 a	20.6	3.4

^aMean of 100 seedlings in 3 replications. ^bMean of 3 replications based on % germination. ^cMean of 15 seedlings used. Means in a column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 1% level. ^dEthyl 3-(3-5-dichloro-phenyl)-5-methyl-2-4-deoxy-5-oxozolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP). ^e1-5-1 (5'-0-carbamoyl-2'' amino 2'' deoxy-L xylonyl)-5'' deoxy-B-D (all furanonyluronic acid)-hydroxy-methyl uracil (Polyoxine AWP).

germination percentage and low infestation percentage (see table). Germination was highest with PCNB, lowest in untreated seeds in inoculated soil. No infection was observed with

benomyl, PCNB, iprodione, and benomyl-iprodione combined. Untreated seeds in inoculated soil showed significantly higher infection than all other treatments. □